

Accessing Skeletal Diversity under Iron Catalysis using Substrate Control: Formation of Pyrroles *versus* Lactones

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Dedicated to Prof. Dr. Julio Alvarez-Builla on the occasion of his 65th birthday.

Abstract: 2-Azetidinone-tethered alkynols and allenols, readily prepared from a propargylidene *b*-lactam aldehyde, were used as starting materials for divergent ring expansion reactions catalyzed by iron(III) chloride. Worthy of note, in contrast to the iron-catalyzed reactions of *b*-lactam allenols which lead to γ -lactones, the reaction of *b*-lactam alkynols under identical conditions gives pyrroles. The gold-catalyzed *6-endo* aminocyclization of these allenic γ -lactones

formed fused dihydropyridines. The iron-catalyzed formation of pyrroles may proceed through a Meyer-Schuster rearrangement followed by *b*-lactam ring opening and cyclization by attack of the amino group to the ketone.

Keywords: alkynes; allenes; iron; pyrroles; rearrangement

Introduction

Iron is the most abundant transition metal on the face of the earth. In addition to playing a pivotal role in biological processes, iron salts have recently emerged as powerful alternatives to other transition metals in the field of catalysis in view of their inexpensiveness and environmental friendliness.^[1] On the other hand, the usual strategies for the preparation of the majority of heterocyclic systems start from the appropriate alicyclic precursor, which after cyclization forms the required heterocycle. An alternative strategy involving the preparation of heterocyclic compounds from smaller-sized heterocycles is very appealing,^[2] because of the additional driving force liberated by strain reduction in ring-enlargement reactions. The inherent strain and their convenient accessibility make *b*-lactams an attractive substrate class. Indeed, *b*-lactams have been recognized as versatile building blocks in organic chemistry for the preparation of natural products and medicinal reagents.^[3] Following up on our combined interest in the area of *b*-lactams and metal catalysis,^[4] herein we report an iron-catalyzed synthesis

of the chemically and biologically relevant pyrrole nucleus, as a convenient alternative to the existing methodologies.^[5] By using the same scaffold but replacing the alkyne by an allene moiety, the reaction proceeded in a different chemoselective fashion,^[6] affording *g*-lactones.^[7]

Results and Discussion

Starting substrates, unsaturated alcohols 2 and 3, were prepared as inseparable *syn/anti* mixtures beginning from 4-oxoazetidone-2-carbaldehyde 1 through carbonyl-addition reactions (Scheme 1). Alkynols 2a and 2b were prepared by the addition of magnesium or lithium acetylides to carbaldehyde 1, using our previous protocol (Scheme 1).^[8] Terminal alkyne 2a was functionalized as its corresponding aryl alkynols 2c and 2d by treatment with iodoarenes under Sonogashira conditions (Scheme 1). Allenols 3a–e were achieved *via* metal-mediated Barbier-type allenylation reactions of *b*-lactam aldehyde 1 in aqueous media following our previously described methodologies,^[9]

Scheme 1. Synthesis of alkynols **2** and allenols **3**. *Reagents and conditions:* i) Ethynylmagnesium bromide, THF, -78 °C, 18 h. ii) Phenylacetylene, *n*-BuLi, THF, -78 °C, 5 h. iii) ArI, 1 mol% Pd(PPh₃)₂Cl₂, 2 mol% CuI, Et₃N, DMSO, 40 °C, 3 h; ArI = 4-iodoanisole; 2d: ArI = 2-iodothiophene; 2e: ArI = 1-bromo-4-iodobenzene. iv) Appropriate 1-substituted-3-bromopropyne, In, THF, NH₄Cl (aqueous saturated), room temperature, 18 h. v) Ethyl 4-bromobut-2-ynoate, In, LiI, DMF, 40 °C, 69 h. vi) Propargyl bromide, SnCl₂·2H₂O, LiI·3H₂O, DMF, room temperature, 48 h. PMP = 4-MeOC₆H₄, Tph = 2-thiophenyl.

Scheme 2. Chemodivergent iron-catalyzed reactions of enallenes **3a** and **4**. *Reagents and conditions:* i) 10 mol% FeCl₃, DCE, sealed tube, 80 °C, 1.5 h. PMP = 4-MeOC₆H₄, DCE = 1,2-dichloroethane.

while allenols **3f** and **3g** were prepared through Barbier-type protocols adopting modified literature methods.^[10]

We have recently outlined the chemodifferentiation between alkene and allene moieties using iron catalysis in substrates of type **4** (Scheme 2).^[11] To further explore modes of reactivity of unsaturated hydroxy-*b*-lactams under Fe(III) catalysis, we have screened their reactions using a diverse set of substrates. With the requirement that iron salts be the catalytic metal source, we began to address the reactivity of unsaturated alcohols **2** and **3** under FeCl₃-catalysis. Enallene **3a** was chosen as a model substrate. The outcome of this reaction is, however, unexpected, as the obtained product is not the expected *b*-lactam-fused tetrahydrofuran **5**, but rather its isomeric *g*-lactone **6a** (Scheme 2).^[12] The structure and stereochemistry of the *g*-lactone **6a** were determined by single crystal X-ray diffraction

analysis.^[13] The single crystal structure analysis is in contrast to the structural assignment based on NMR data of this compound in ref.^[11] which has been rectified in a corrigendum.^[11] Apparently, under the given reaction conditions, the carbonyl group displays a more pronounced electrophilicity than the tetrasubstituted alkene moiety; affording the *g*-lactone through N-1/C-2 amide bond cleavage with concomitant rearrangement.

With the optimal reaction conditions established, the scope of this rearrangement reaction was then studied. Scheme 3 shows the results for six different related enallenes, demonstrating that the transformation from Scheme 2 is general under the chosen reaction conditions of iron catalysis, affording *g*-lactone derivatives **6b–g** in moderate yields regardless of electronic

Scheme 3. Iron-catalyzed preparation of *g*-lactones **6** from 2-azetidione-tethered allenic alcohols **3**. *Reagents and conditions:* i) 10 mol% FeCl₃, DCE, sealed tube, 80 °C, **6b**: 2 h; **6c**: 1.5 h; **6d**: 1.5 h; **6e**: 2 h; **6f**: 2 h; **6g**: 1 h. ii) NIS, acetone/H₂O (3:1), room temperature, 4 h. PMP = 4-MeOC₆H₄, DCE = 1,2-dichloroethane.

and steric effects at the allene. Replacement of the methyl group at the allene moiety by hydrogen or aryl groups also afforded the corresponding products. For this set of substrates, the reaction proceeded with complete chemoselectivity in favour of *g*-lactone formation. Noteworthy, the allenic group is kept unaltered under the reactions conditions. Curiously, the anisyl group of *g*-lactone derivative **6a** could be readily converted into a hydroxyphenyl moiety in *g*-lactone **7** by *N*-iodosuccinimide (NIS) treatment (Scheme 3).

Given their widespread applications as building blocks in organic synthesis, allenes are of increasing importance.^[14] Among numerous synthetic utilities, the hydroamination of the unsaturated C=C bonds is of fundamental significance.^[15] Although allenes are more reactive in metal-catalyzed hydroamination reactions than alkenes, regioselectivity problems are significant. The use of gold salts has gained a lot of attention in the recent times because of their powerful soft Lewis acidic nature.^[16] In particular, gold activation of allenes toward attacks by nitrogen nucleophiles is an important C–N bond-forming reaction.^[17] However, effective gold-catalyzed protocols for free amines have not yet been readily available,^[18] because the high ligating ability of amines may cause deactivation of the catalyst by the basic amine. Despite the anticipated difficulty, we decided to test the reactivity of our allenic *g*-lactones under gold-catalyzed conditions. The stage was thus set for the gold-catalyzed reaction of *g*-lactone allenamine **6a**. Preliminary studies about the catalytic activity of gold(I) chloride complexes [AuCl, (Ph₃P)AuCl] in the presence or absence of different additives [AgOTf, pyridine] were frustrating. Fortunately, under AuCl₃ exposure the reaction took place, affording bicycle **8a** in fair yield, using 40 mol% loading (Scheme 4). However, when the loading of the catalyst was lowered to 10 mol%, only 20% conversion was observed. Interestingly, along with bicycle **8a**, chloro derivative **9a** was also obtained as by-product in the AuCl₃-promoted reaction. The formation of fused dihydropyridine *g*-lactone **8a** can

Scheme 4. Gold-promoted preparation of tetrahydrofuro[3,2-*b*]pyridin-2-ones **8** and chloroarenes **9** from 2-furanone-tethered allenic amines. *Reagents and conditions:* i) 40 or 50 mol% AuCl₃, CH₂Cl₂, sealed tube, 60 °C, **6a**: 94 h; **6b**: 97 h; **6g**: 28 h. PMP = 4-MeOC₆H₄.

be explained through a totally regioselective 6-*endo*-trig allenic aminocyclization. More troublesome is the explanation for the obtention of chloroarene **9a**. We therefore speculated how the presence of a different substituent at the allene moiety may influence the reactivity. Consequently, replacement of the methyl group at the allenic site by hydrogen or phenyl moieties was studied. Thus, phenyl-substituted allene **6b** was exposed to gold(III) reaction conditions. In this case, the reaction took place selectively, giving exclusively chloroarene **9b**, but the reaction product could only be obtained in reasonable yield using a higher catalyst loading of 50 mol% (Scheme 4). Gratifyingly, unsubstituted allene **6g** was found to be the best partner of gold for the hydroamination reaction, because its exposure to AuCl₃ provided bicycle **8g** as the sole product (Scheme 4).

A possible pathway for the achievement of fused dihydropyridine derivatives **8** from *b*-allenamines **6** may initially involve the formation of a complex **6**-AuCl₃ through coordination of the gold trichloride to the distal allenic double bond. Next, regioselective 6-*endo* aminoauration forms zwitterionic species **10**. Loss of HCl followed by protonolysis of the carbon-gold bond of **11** affords bicycles **8** and regenerates the

Scheme 5. Mechanistic explanation for the Au-catalyzed preparation of fused dihydropyridines **8**. PMP = 4-MeOC₆H₄.

gold catalyst (Scheme 5). A conceivable mechanism for the chlorination of the aromatic ring (obtention of chloroarenes **9** from **6**) could result from an electrophilic aromatic substitution,^[19] in which the gold is highly Lewis acidic and the electron-rich aromatic ring attacks gold-bound chloride.^[20] The Au(III) might be activated toward chloride donation by the substrate. In this mechanistic picture, the role of

AuCl₃ is not restricted to a *p*-acidic gold catalyst, because it also acts as a reactant in this reaction.

It was envisaged that if the allene functionality is replaced by an alkyne moiety, the analogous lactonization would give rise to amino-substituted alkyne derivatives. We initially examined the iron-catalyzed reaction of alkyne **2a**. In the presence of FeCl₃, the reactions conditions successfully used for the obtention of allenic *g*-lactones **6**, we found the reaction of **2a** proceeded smoothly. Surprisingly, the expected alkynic *g*-lactone **12a** was obtained in just 9% yield. In addition, a chromatographically separable 1,2-disubstituted pyrrole **13a** was also isolated in 44% yield (Scheme 6). To shed light on the ring expansion, the reaction of alkyne **2a** was tested in the presence of different Lewis acids. Different metallic halides (HfCl₄, BiCl₃, etc.) gave *g*-lactone **12a** without formation of any pyrrole derivative (Scheme 6). Only FeCl₃ showed catalytic activity towards pyrrole obtention.

The *α*-vinylpyrrole substructure is the core of a number of biologically relevant compounds, such as sunitinib, a promising kinase inhibitor and antitumor agent.^[21] Besides, *C*-vinylated pyrroles are important building blocks for forming porphyrins and related nitrogen macrocycles as well as for serving as precursors for photoactive polymeric materials.^[22] As a consequence, the unexpected skeletal reorganization to *α*-vinylpyrrole formation triggered our interest. As revealed in Scheme 6 and Scheme 7, different *b*-lactam alkyne derivatives were suitable for this transformation, affording pyrrole derivatives **13a–e** in moderate to good yields regardless of electronic and steric effects. Starting from non-terminal alkynes **2**, 1,2,5-trisubstituted

Scheme 6. Diverse Lewis acid-catalyzed 2-azetidinone-tethered alkyne rearrangements. *Reagents and conditions*: i) 10 mol% HfCl₄, DCE, sealed tube, 85 °C, 2.5 h. ii) 10 mol% FeCl₃, DCE, sealed tube, 85 °C, 1 h. PMP = 4-MeOC₆H₄, DCE = 1,2-dichloroethane.

Scheme 7. Iron-catalyzed ring expansion reaction of aryl-substituted 2-azetidinone-tethered alkynes **2b–e**; synthesis of 1,2,5-trisubstituted pyrroles **13b–e**. *Reagents and conditions*: i) (a) 10 mol% FeCl₃, DCE, sealed tube, 85 °C, 1 h; (b) DBU, MeI, CHCl₃, room temperature, 1.5 h. ii) 10 mol% FeCl₃, DCE, sealed tube, 85 °C, 1 h. PMP = 4-MeOC₆H₄, DCE = 1,2-dichloroethane, DBU = 1,8-diazabicyclo[5.4.0]undec-7-ene.

Scheme 8. Iron-catalyzed ring expansion reaction of bis(alkynyl-*b*-lactams) 14a and 14b; synthesis of bipyrroles 15a and 15b. *Reagents and conditions:* i) Cu(OAc)₂, K₂CO₃, MeCN, room temperature, 3 h. ii) (a) 10 mol% FeCl₃, DCE, sealed tube, 85 °C, 1 h; (b) DBU, MeI, CHCl₃, room temperature, 1.5 h. iii) 1,4-Diiodobenzene, 1 mol% Pd(PPh₃)₂Cl₂, 2 mol% CuI, Et₃N, DMSO, 40 °C, 2.5 h. PMP = 4-MeOC₆H₄; DCE = 1,2-dichloroethane, DBU = 1,8-diazabicyclo[5.4.0]undec-7-ene.

pyrroles 13b–e were obtained as the sole isolable products, except for 13b (69%) which was accompanied by a small amount of lactone 12b (9%). 2-Azetidinone-tethered alkyne 2c containing an electron-donating group on the benzene ring (methoxy at the *para* position) gave 53% yield of pyrrole 12c. Other heteroaromatic systems, such as thiophen-2-yl-substituted alkyne 2d, could be employed in this reaction, and the corresponding pyrrolic product 12d was obtained. Pyrrole 13e was isolated as the methyl ester due to the difficulty encountered in purifying the high polar carboxylic acid. The formation of these pyrroles indicates an important feature, namely, it reveals that the nature of the unsaturated group at the carbinolic center does have an electronic influence on the course of the ring expansion process, stressing the importance of an alkyne *versus* allene group to drive the ring expansion towards pyrrole ring construction. Fine-tuning of reactivity and selectivity by the substitution of the parent compound is an important goal.^[23]

To demonstrate that the above protocol can be considered in complex synthetic planning, it was successfully used for the double-ring expansion of bis(alkynyl-*b*-lactams) 14a and 14b to bipyrroles 15a and 15b. Bipyrroles are attractive structures not only because they are key subunits in important natural products but also are known for their conducting properties.^[24] To screen the reactivity of the bis(alkynyl) moiety, homodimerization of alkyne 2a was studied in the presence of a copper promoter. The homodimerization reaction proceeded smoothly to afford the desired diyne 14a by using modified classical copper promoted conditions (Scheme 8).^[25] Copper(II) acetate in combination with potassium carbonate in acetonitrile

gave the best performance. Bis(alkynyl-*b*-lactam) 14b was prepared by treatment of 2 equivalents of alkyne 2a with 1,4-diiodobenzene through a double Sonogashira coupling reaction (Scheme 8). As shown in Scheme 8, bis(alkynyl-*b*-lactams) 14a and 14b also participate in this chemistry, leading to bipyrroles 15a and 15b upon sequential FeCl₃ treatment and esterification. The reactions were so chemoselective that signal for *g*-lactone protons were not observed in the ¹H NMR spectra of the unpurified reaction mixtures. Compounds 15 are remarkable since they bear a challenging dimeric pyrrole structure.

Since reactions involving iron(III) trichloride may generate HCl, the possibility exists that *in situ* generated HCl may catalyze the rearrangement reaction. However, when 10 mol% of HCl was used as the catalyst under identical conditions, no pyrrole product was observed, thereby ruling out the possible HCl catalysis. The role of the iron salt seems obvious, and a Brønsted acid catalysis for the ring expansion reaction seems very unlikely. Probably, FeCl₃ enhances the reactivity of the alkyne moiety through selective formal 1,3-hydroxy shift (Meyer–Schuster rearrangement).^[26] A plausible mechanism based on a cascade rearrangement is outlined in Scheme 9. In the presence of FeCl₃, a Meyer–Schuster intermediate 16 is produced from alkynols 2, which may generate the amino ketone species 17 after tautomerization and *b*-lactam ring opening. The amine group of species 17 might then undergo nucleophilic attack to the ketone moiety to afford species 18. Finally, dehydration followed by demetalation yield heterocycles 13 and regenerate the iron catalyst (Scheme 9). The pyrrole formation must be driven by relief of the strain asso-

Scheme 9. Proposed catalytic cycle for the iron-catalyzed formation of pyrroles 13 from alkynyl-*b*-lactams 2.

ciated with the four-membered ring on forming a more stable five-membered ring.

Conclusions

In conclusion, an unprecedented and divergent route to *g*-lactone and pyrrole derivatives *via* iron-catalyzed tandem ring-opening/closing reactions of 2-azetidinone-tethered alkynols and allenols has been developed. This strategy offers a concise platform for the construction of five-membered ring systems under mild conditions with high atom economy. A further gold-catalyzed access to fused dihydropyridines was also developed. Further investigation on the range of the current reaction is in progress.

Experimental Section

General Methods

¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker AMX-500, Bruker Avance-300, Varian VRX-300S or Bruker AC-200. NMR spectra were recorded in CDCl₃ solutions, except where otherwise stated. Chemical shifts are given in ppm relative to TMS (¹H, 0.0 ppm), or CDCl₃ (¹³C, 77.0 ppm). Low- and high-resolution mass spectra were taken on an Agilent 6520 Accurate-Mass QTOF LC/MS spectrometer using the electronic impact (EI) or electro-spray modes (ES) unless otherwise stated. IR spectra were recorded on a Bruker Tensor 27 spectrometer. Specific rotations [α]_D are given in 10⁻¹ deg cm² g⁻¹ at 20 °C, and the concentration (*c*) is expressed in g per 100 mL. All commercially available compounds were used without further purification.

General Procedure for the Fe(III)-Catalyzed Rearrangement of 2-Azetidinone-Tethered Allenic Alcohols 3; Preparation of *g*-Lactones 6

FeCl₃ (0.10 mmol) was added to a stirred solution of the corresponding allenol 3 (1.0 mmol) in 1,2-dichloroethane (10 mL). The resulting mixture was heated at 80 °C in a sealed tube until complete disappearance (TLC) of the starting material. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool to room temperature and then was quenched with aqueous saturated NH₄Cl (1.0 mL). The mixture was extracted with ethyl acetate (3 × 5 mL), and the combined extracts were washed twice with brine. The organic layer was dried (MgSO₄) and concentrated under reduced pressure. Chromatography of the residue eluting with ethyl acetate/hexanes mixtures gave analytically pure *g*-lactones 6.^[27]

g-Lactone 6a: From 100 mg (0.34 mmol) of 2-azetidinone-tethered allenic alcohol 3a, and chromatography of the residue using hexanes/ethyl acetate (3:1) as eluent gave compound 6a as a colorless solid; yield: 87 mg (87%); mp 118–120 °C (hexanes/ethyl acetate); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃, 25 °C): δ = 6.81 and 6.57 (d, *J* = 9.0 Hz, each 2H), 4.89 (m, 2H), 4.72 (br s, 1H), 4.62 (br s, 1H), 3.76 (s, 3H), 2.35 and 2.00 (s, each 3H), 1.77 (t, *J* = 3.2 Hz, 3H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃, 25 °C): δ = 205.9, 169.1, 157.7, 152.9, 121.7, 115.2, 114.8, 98.1, 81.7, 77.2, 57.0, 55.8, 24.1, 20.5, 15.1; IR (CHCl₃): ν = 3367, 1958, 1743 cm⁻¹; HR-MS (ES): *m/z* = 322.1420, calcd. for C₁₈H₂₁NNaO₃ [*M* + Na]⁺: 322.1419.

g-Lactone 6b: From 85 mg (0.23 mmol) of 2-azetidinone-tethered allenic alcohol 3 b, and chromatography of the residue using hexanes/ethyl acetate (3:1) as eluent gave compound 6b as a colorless oil; yield: 47 mg (56%); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃, 25 °C): δ = 7.34 (m, 5H), 6.76 and 6.53 (d, *J* = 9.0 Hz, each 2H), 5.33 (m, 3H), 4.73 (br s, 1H), 3.75 (s, 3H), 2.34 and 1.98 (s, each 3H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃, 25 °C): δ = 207.7, 166.7, 164.4, 153.0, 133.0, 128.6, 127.6, 126.6, 121.4, 115.1, 113.8, 105.6, 81.4, 77.2, 60.4, 55.7, 24.2, 20.5; IR (CHCl₃): ν = 3364, 1955, 1741 cm⁻¹; HR-MS (ES): *m/z* = 362.1752, calcd. for C₂₃H₂₄NO₃ [*M* + H]⁺: 362.1756.

g-Lactone 6c: From 50 mg (0.13 mmol) of 2-azetidinone-tethered allenic alcohol 3c, and chromatography of the residue using hexanes/ethyl acetate (3:1) as eluent gave compound 6c as a colorless oil; yield: 28 mg (55%); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃, 25 °C): δ = 7.33 and 6.87 (d, *J* = 9.0 Hz, each 2H), 6.77 and 6.51 (d, *J* = 9.0 Hz, each 2H), 5.30 (m, 2H), 5.23 (br s, 1H), 4.71 (br s, 1H), 3.81 (s, 3H), 3.74 (s, 3H), 2.34 and 1.98 (s, each 3H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃, 25 °C): δ = 207.4, 159.1, 157.8, 152.9, 151.1, 128.0, 125.2, 121.7, 115.1, 115.0, 114.1, 105.2, 81.3, 78.8, 57.7, 55.7, 55.3, 24.1, 20.5; IR (CHCl₃): ν = 3370, 1948, 1742 cm⁻¹; HR-MS (ES): *m/z* = 392.1853, calcd. for C₂₄H₂₆NO₄ [*M* + H]⁺: 392.1862.

g-Lactone 6d: From 50 mg (0.14 mmol) of 2-azetidinone-tethered allenic alcohol 3d, and chromatography of the residue using hexanes/ethyl acetate (3:1) as eluent gave compound 6d as a colorless oil; yield: 25 mg (49%); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃, 25 °C): δ = 7.24 (dd, *J* = 5.0, 1.3 Hz, 1H), 7.00 (m, 2H), 6.80 and 6.53 (d, *J* = 9.0 Hz, each 2H), 5.35 (m, 2H), 5.17 (td, *J* = 2.2, 1.0 Hz, 1H), 4.71 (br s, 1H), 3.75 (s, 3H), 3.34 (s, 3H), 2.34 and 1.99 (s, each 3H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃, 25 °C): δ = 206.9, 168.9, 158.1, 153.0, 136.6, 127.7, 125.4, 125.1, 121.4, 115.1, 113.9, 101.6, 82.0, 79.3, 57.7,

55.7, 24.2, 20.6; IR (CHCl₃): $\nu = 3364, 1951, 1743 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; HR- MS (ES): $m/z = 368.1304$, calcd. for C₂₁H₂₂NO₃S [M + H]⁺: 368.1320.

g-Lactone 6e: From 50 mg (0.128 mmol) of 2-azetidinone-tethered allenic alcohol 3e, and chromatography of the residue using hexanes/ethyl acetate (3:1) as eluent gave compound 6e as a colorless oil; yield: 28 mg (54%); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃, 25 °C): $\delta = 7.34$ (m, 5 H), 6.77 and 6.60 (d, $J = 9.0$ Hz, each 2 H), 5.04 (m, 2 H), 4.94 (br s, 1 H), 4.73 (br s, 1 H), 4.51 (s, 2 H), 3.74 (s, 3 H), 2.30 and 1.92 (s, each 3 H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃, 25 °C): $\delta = 206.8, 167.9, 157.8, 137.7, 128.6, 128.4, 127.8, 127.7, 126.9, 120.7, 115.2, 100.4, 78.8, 77.2, 72.4, 68.4, 60.4, 55.8, 24.1, 20.5$; IR (CHCl₃): $\nu = 3364, 1954, 1744 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; HR-MS (ES): $m/z = 406.2017$, calcd. for C₂₅H₂₈NO₄ [M + H]⁺: 406.2018.

g-Lactone 6f: From 32 mg (0.09 mmol) of 2-azetidinone-tethered allenic alcohol 3f, and chromatography of the residue using hexanes/ethyl acetate (3:1) as eluent gave compound 6f as a colorless oil; yield: 16 mg (49%); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃, 25 °C): $\delta = 7.36$ and 6.90 (d, $J = 9.0$ Hz, each 2 H), 5.37 (t, $J = 1.5$ Hz, 1 H), 5.31 (m, 1 H), 5.20 (dd, $J = 1.5, 1.0$ Hz, 1 H), 4.44 (d, $J = 0.9$ Hz, 1 H), 4.24 (q, $J = 7.0$ Hz, 2 H), 3.80 (s, 3 H), 1.62 and 1.27 (s, each 3 H), 1.31 (t, $J = 7.0$ Hz, 3 H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃, 25 °C): $\delta = 207.6, 179.2, 164.8, 158.1, 153.0, 125.1, 117.9, 114.6, 109.8, 94.4, 80.5, 77.2, 69.3, 60.7, 55.5, 24.2, 21.6, 14.1$; IR (CHCl₃): $\nu = 3365, 1952, 1745, 1718 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; HR-MS (ES): $m/z = 358.1652$, calcd. for C₂₀H₂₄NO₅ [M + H]⁺: 358.1654.

g-Lactone 6g: From 54 mg (0.19 mmol) of 2-azetidinone-tethered allenic alcohol 3g, and chromatography of the residue using hexanes/ethyl acetate (3:1) as eluent gave compound 6g as a colorless oil; yield: 33 mg (60%); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃, 25 °C): $\delta = 6.82$ and 6.56 (d, $J = 9.0$ Hz, each 2 H), 5.34 (q, $J = 6.3$ Hz, 1 H), 5.01 (m, 2 H), 4.86 (dtd, $J = 6.2, 2.5, 0.9$ Hz, 1 H), 4.53 (br s, 1 H), 3.77 (s, 3 H), 3.66 (br s, 1 H), 2.36 and 2.02 (s, each 3 H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃, 25 °C): $\delta = 207.9, 169.0, 158.6, 152.7, 139.6, 121.1, 115.1, 114.5, 90.3, 78.6, 78.5, 57.8, 55.7, 24.2, 20.5$; IR (CHCl₃): $\nu = 3360, 1950, 1743 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; HR-MS (ES): $m/z = 286.1438$, calcd. for C₁₇H₂₀NO₃ [M + H]⁺: 286.1443.

General Procedure for the Gold-Catalyzed Reaction of 2-Furanone-Tethered Allenic Amines 6; Preparation of Compounds 8 and 9

AuCl₃ (0.4–0.5 mmol) was added to a stirred solution of the corresponding 2-furanone-tethered allenic amine 6 (1.0 mmol) in dichloromethane (10 mL) under argon. The resulting mixture was heated at 60 °C in a sealed tube until complete disappearance (TLC) of the starting material. The reaction was then quenched with brine (2 mL), the mixture was extracted with ethyl acetate (3 × 5 mL), and the combined extracts were washed twice with brine. The organic layer was dried (MgSO₄) and concentrated under reduced pressure. Chromatography of the residue eluting with ethyl acetate/hexanes mixtures gave analytically pure adducts 8 and 9.

Preparation of Bicycle 8a and Chloro Derivative 9a

From 45 mg (0.15 mmol) of allenic amine 6a, and after chromatography of the residue using hexanes/ethyl acetate (4:1)

as eluent, 20 mg (45%) of the less polar compound 8a and 10 mg (20%) of the more polar compound 9a were obtained.

Bicycle 8a: Pale brown oil; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃, 25 °C): $\delta = 6.82$ and 6.62 (d, $J = 9.0$ Hz, each 2 H), 5.76 (m, 1 H), 4.74 (s, 1 H), 4.41 (br s, 1 H), 4.11 (m, 2 H), 3.77 (s, 3 H), 2.37 and 2.02 (s, each 3 H), 1.70 (t, $J = 1.3$ Hz, 3 H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃, 25 °C): $\delta = 169.1, 164.0, 147.8, 138.2, 124.6, 115.9, 115.1, 97.6, 77.2, 57.8, 55.7, 39.3, 24.4, 20.6, 11.6$; IR (CHCl₃): $\nu = 1752 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; HR-MS (ES): $m/z = 300.1594$, calcd. for C₁₈H₂₂NO₃ [M + H]⁺: 300.1600.

Chloro derivative 9a: Pale brown oil; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃, 25 °C): $\delta = 6.93$ (d, $J = 2.8$ Hz, 1 H), 6.77 (dd, $J = 9.0, 2.8$ Hz, 1 H), 6.56 (d, $J = 9.0$ Hz, 1 H), 4.89 (m, 2 H), 4.68 (s, 1 H), 4.64 (br s, 1 H), 3.76 (s, 3 H), 2.38 and 2.00 (s, each 3 H), 1.78 (t, $J = 3.2$ Hz, 3 H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃, 25 °C): $\delta = 205.9, 160.5, 158.5, 152.2, 136.2, 121.4, 120.4, 115.8, 113.8, 112.6, 98.1, 82.1, 77.5, 56.7, 55.9, 24.2, 20.6, 15.1$; IR (CHCl₃, cm⁻¹): $\nu = 3370, 1954, 1740 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; HRMS (ES): calcd. for C₁₈H₂₁NClO₃ [M + H]⁺: 334.1210; found: 334.1202.

Chloro derivative 9b: From 30 mg (0.09 mmol) of allenic amine 6b, and chromatography of the residue using hexanes/ethyl acetate (4:1) as eluent gave compound 9b as a pale brown oil; yield: 18 mg (52%); ¹H NMR (700 MHz, CDCl₃, 25 °C): $\delta = 7.42$ (d, $J = 7.7$ Hz, 3 H), 7.34 (t, $J = 7.7$ Hz, 2 H), 6.93 (d, $J = 2.8$ Hz, 1 H), 6.65 (dd, $J = 9.0, 2.8$ Hz, 1 H), 6.39 (d, $J = 9.0$ Hz, 1 H), 5.35 (m, 2 H), 5.24 (s, 1 H), 4.75 (s, 1 H), 3.74 (s, 3 H), 2.38 and 1.98 (s, each 3 H); ¹³C NMR (175 MHz, CDCl₃, 25 °C): $\delta = 207.7, 168.8, 158.6, 152.3, 136.0, 133.1, 128.7, 127.8, 126.9, 121.3, 120.6, 115.8, 113.8, 113.0, 105.7, 81.6, 79.1, 57.4, 56.0, 24.2, 20.7$; IR (CHCl₃, cm⁻¹): $\nu = 3372, 1952, 1742 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; HR-MS (ES): $m/z = 396.1356$, calcd. for C₂₃H₂₃NClO₃ [M + H]⁺: 396.1366.

Bicycle 8g: From 45 mg (0.16 mmol) of allenic amine 6g, and chromatography of the residue using hexanes/ethyl acetate (4:1) as eluent gave compound 8g as a pale brown oil; yield: 22 mg (49%); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃, 25 °C): $\delta = 6.83$ and 6.55 (d, $J = 9.0$ Hz, each 2 H), 6.07 (dt, $J = 9.1, 1.3$ Hz, 1 H), 4.98 (dd, $J = 9.1, 1.2$ Hz, 1 H), 4.40 (dd, $J = 2.5, 1.5$ Hz, 2 H), 4.36 (br s, 1 H), 3.77 (s, 3 H), 3.60 (br s, 1 H), 2.38 and 2.03 (s, each 3 H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃, 25 °C): $\delta = 168.8, 159.5, 153.2, 139.2, 134.1, 120.8, 115.5, 115.3, 104.8, 85.6, 58.4, 55.8, 53.1, 24.4, 20.7$; IR (CHCl₃): $\nu = 1750 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; HR-MS (ES): $m/z = 286.1448$, calcd. for C₁₇H₂₀NO₃ [M + H]⁺: 286.1443.

General Procedure for the Fe(III)-Catalyzed Rearrangement of 2-Azetidinone-Tethered Alkynols 2; Preparation of (Pyrrolyl)butenoic Acids 13

FeCl₃ (0.10 mmol) was added to a stirred solution of the corresponding alkynol 2 (1.0 mmol) in 1,2-dichloroethane (10 mL). The resulting mixture was heated at 85 °C in a sealed tube until complete disappearance (TLC) of the starting material. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool to room temperature, and then was quenched with aqueous saturated NH₄Cl (1.0 mL). The mixture was extracted with ethyl acetate (3 × 5 mL), and the combined extracts were washed twice with brine. The organic layer was dried (MgSO₄) and concentrated under reduced pressure. Chromatography of the residue eluting with ethyl acetate/hexanes mixtures gave analytically pure pyrroles 13.

Preparation of g-Lactone 12a and Pyrrole 13a

From 42 mg (0.15 mmol) of alkynol 2a, and after chromatography of the residue using hexanes/ethyl acetate (2:1) as eluent, 4 mg (9%) of the less polar compound 12a and 19 mg (44%) of the more polar compound 13a were obtained.

g-Lactone 12a: Colorless oil; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (300 MHz, CDCl_3 , 25 °C): δ =6.85 and 6.60 (d, J =9.0 Hz, each 2H), 4.94 (s, 1H), 4.66 (br s, 1H), 3.77 (s, 3H), 2.69 (d, J =2.2 Hz, 1H), 2.38 and 2.05 (s, each 3H), 1.60 (br s, 1H); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (75 MHz, CDCl_3 , 25 °C): δ =159.9, 122.2, 119.9, 115.3, 114.0, 110.6, 108.4, 79.8, 70.9, 59.8, 55.7, 55.4, 24.4, 20.6; IR (CHCl_3): ν =3392, 2125, 1748 cm^{-1} ; MS (EI): m/z (%) = 271 (100) [M] $^+$.

Pyrrole 13a: Pale red solid; mp 160–162 °C (hexanes/ethyl acetate); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (300 MHz, CDCl_3 , 25 °C): δ =7.18 and 6.87 (d, J =9.0 Hz, each 2H), 6.85 (m, 1H), 6.30 (dd, J =3.2, 2.9 Hz, 1H), 6.16 (dd, J =3.4, 1.7 Hz, 1H), 3.82 (s, 3H), 2.11 and 1.66 (s, each 3H); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (75 MHz, CDCl_3 , 25 °C): δ =171.3, 158.2, 156.4, 129.0, 126.3, 122.2, 120.5, 114.0, 110.6, 108.4, 55.4, 25.2, 22.6; IR (CHCl_3): ν =3210, 1705 cm^{-1} ; HR-MS (ES): m/z =272.1281, calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{18}\text{NO}_3$ [$M+H$] $^+$: 272.1287.

Preparation of g-Lactone 12b and Pyrrole 13b

From 73 mg (0.21 mmol) of alkynol 2b, and after chromatography of the residue using hexanes/ethyl acetate (2:1) as eluent, 7 mg (9%) of the less polar compound 12b and 51 mg (69%) of the more polar compound 13b were obtained.

g-Lactone 12b: Colorless oil; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (300 MHz, CDCl_3 , 25 °C): δ =7.50 (m, 2H), 7.36 (m, 3H), 6.86 and 6.64 (d, J =9.0 Hz, each 2H), 5.16 (d, J =1.0 Hz, 1H), 4.73 (br s, 1H), 3.78 (s, 3H), 2.40 and 2.07 (s, each 3H); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (75 MHz, CDCl_3 , 25 °C): δ =168.6, 159.5, 153.0, 139.3, 131.9, 129.1, 128.4 (2CH Ph), 121.6, 120.4, 115.3, 114.5, 87.8, 84.9, 71.9, 60.0, 55.8, 24.4, 20.6; IR (CHCl_3): ν =3385, 1750 cm^{-1} ; HR-MS (ES): m/z =348.1594, calcd. for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{22}\text{NO}_3$ [$M+H$] $^+$: 348.1600.

Pyrrole 13b: Pale red solid; mp 160–162 °C (hexanes/ethyl acetate); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (300 MHz, CDCl_3 , 25 °C): δ =7.13 (m, 5H), 7.02 and 6.77 (d, J =9.0 Hz, each 2H), 6.45 (d, J =3.5 Hz, 1H), 6.19 (d, J =3.7 Hz, 1H), 3.77 (s, 3H), 2.09 and 1.76 (s, each 3H); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (75 MHz, CDCl_3 , 25 °C): δ =172.0, 158.4, 156.2, 134.4, 133.3, 131.9, 131.8, 129.2, 128.0, 127.9, 125.8, 121.2, 113.7, 110.0, 109.1, 55.3, 25.5, 22.6; IR (CHCl_3): ν =3214, 1704 cm^{-1} ; HR-MS (ES): m/z =348.1596, calcd. for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{22}\text{NO}_3$ [$M+H$] $^+$: 348.1600.

Pyrrole 13c: From 70 mg (0.20 mmol) of alkynol 2c, and chromatography of the residue using hexanes/ethyl acetate (2:1) as eluent gave compound 13c as a pale red solid; yield: 37 mg (53%); mp 179–181 °C (hexanes/ethyl acetate); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (300 MHz, CDCl_3 , 25 °C): δ =7.01 and 6.76 (d, J =9.0 Hz, each 2H), 7.00 and 6.71 (d, J =9.0 Hz, each 2H), 6.36 (d, J =3.5 Hz, 1H), 6.17 (d, J =3.5 Hz, 1H), 3.77 (s, 3H), 3.75 (s, 3H), 2.08 and 1.74 (s, each 3H); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (75 MHz, CDCl_3 , 25 °C): δ =171.5, 158.3, 157.8, 155.7, 134.3, 131.9, 131.1, 129.3, 129.2, 126.0, 121.4, 113.7, 113.4, 109.8, 108.2, 55.3, 55.1, 25.4, 22.5; IR (CHCl_3): ν =3220, 1700 cm^{-1} ; HR-MS (ES): m/z =378.1701, calcd. for $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{24}\text{NO}_4$ [$M+H$] $^+$: 378.1705.

Pyrrole 13d: From 71 mg (0.14 mmol) of alkynol 2d, and chromatography of the residue using hexanes/ethyl acetate

(2:1) as eluent gave compound 13d as a pale red solid; yield: 33 mg (47%); mp 170–172 °C (hexanes/ethyl acetate); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (300 MHz, CDCl_3 , 25 °C): δ =7.11 and 6.83 (d, J =9.0 Hz, each 2H), 7.02 (dd, J =5.1, 1.0 Hz, 1H), 6.81 (dd, J =5.1, 3.6 Hz, 1H), 6.51 (d, J =3.5 Hz, 2H), 6.15 (d, J =3.7 Hz, 1H), 3.81 (s, 3H), 2.10 and 1.82 (s, each 3H); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (75 MHz, CDCl_3 , 25 °C): δ =171.2, 159.2, 157.0, 135.6, 132.0, 131.2, 129.9, 128.5, 126.8, 123.6, 123.4, 113.8, 109.9, 109.0, 55.3, 25.6, 22.6; IR (CHCl_3): ν =3228, 1704 cm^{-1} ; HR-MS (ES): m/z =354.1167, calcd. for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{NO}_3\text{S}$ [$M+H$] $^+$: 354.1164.

General Procedure for the Fe(III)-Catalyzed Rearrangement of Alkynol 2e and Bis(alkynols) 14; Preparation of (Pyrrolyl)butenoates 13e and 15

FeCl_3 (0.10 mmol) was added to a stirred solution of the corresponding mono- or bis-alkynol 2e or 14 (1.0 mmol) in 1,2-dichloroethane (10 mL). The resulting mixture was heated at 85 °C in a sealed tube until complete disappearance (TLC) of the starting material. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool to room temperature, and then was quenched with brine (2 mL). The mixture was extracted with ethyl acetate (3 × 5 mL), and the combined extracts were washed twice with brine. The organic layer was dried (MgSO_4) and concentrated under reduced pressure. The crude (pyrrolyl)-butenoic acid was solved in chloroform (0.8 mL) and 1,8-diazabicyclo[5.4.0]undec-7-ene (304 mg, 2.0 mmol) was slowly added at 0 °C under argon atmosphere. The reaction mixture was stirred for 30 min at room temperature and then was recooled at 0 °C. Methyl iodide (2.8 mmol) was added and the mixture was stirred for 1 h at room temperature. The reaction was then quenched with aqueous saturated NH_4Cl (1.0 mL), the mixture was extracted with ethyl acetate (3 × 5 mL), and the combined extracts were washed twice with brine. The organic layer was dried (MgSO_4) and concentrated under reduced pressure. Chromatography of the residue eluting with ethyl acetate/hexanes mixtures gave analytically pure pyrroles 13e and 15.

Pyrrole 13e: From 32 mg (0.075 mmol) of alkynol 2e, and chromatography of the residue using hexanes/ethyl acetate (3:1) as eluent gave compound 13e as a pale red oil; yield: 17 mg (52%); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (300 MHz, CDCl_3 , 25 °C): δ =7.28 and 6.93 (d, J =9.0 Hz, each 2H), 6.94 and 6.80 (d, J =9.0 Hz, each 2H), 6.44 (d, J =3.6 Hz, 1H), 6.17 (d, J =3.6 Hz, 1H), 3.81 (s, 3H), 3.45 (s, 3H), 2.10 and 1.85 (s, each 3H); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (75 MHz, CDCl_3 , 25 °C): δ =167.4, 158.5, 153.3, 132.9, 132.6, 132.2, 131.5, 131.1, 129.3, 129.1, 121.4, 119.7, 113.8, 110.5, 109.4, 55.3, 51.3, 25.1, 22.5; IR (CHCl_3): ν =1718 cm^{-1} ; HR-MS (ES): m/z =440.0884, calcd. for $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{23}\text{BrNO}_3$ [$M+H$] $^+$: 440.0861.

Bis(pyrrole) 15a: From 66 mg (0.14 mmol) of bis(alkynol) 14a, and chromatography of the residue using hexanes/ethyl acetate (3:1) as eluent gave compound 15a as a red solid; yield: 41 mg (60%); mp 136–138 °C (hexanes/ethyl acetate); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (300 MHz, CDCl_3 , 25 °C): δ =6.56 and 6.42 (d, J =9.0 Hz, each 4H), 6.34 (d, J =3.5 Hz, 2H), 6.04 (d, J =3.5 Hz, 2H), 3.74 (s, 6H), 3.33 (s, 6H), 2.04 and 1.70 (s, each 6H); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (75 MHz, CDCl_3 , 25 °C): δ =167.3, 157.7, 153.0, 131.7, 130.3, 127.7, 125.9, 121.6, 113.0, 111.3, 109.7, 55.3, 51.1, 24.8, 22.4; IR (CHCl_3): ν =1714 cm^{-1} ; HR-MS (ES): m/z =569.2640, calcd. for $\text{C}_{34}\text{H}_{37}\text{N}_2\text{O}_6$ [$M+H$] $^+$: 569.2652.

Bis(pyrrole) 15b: From 62 mg (0.07 mmol) of bis(alkynol) 14b, and chromatography of the residue using hexanes/ethyl acetate (6:1) as eluent gave compound 15b as a pale red oil; yield: 35 mg (54%); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (700 MHz, CDCl_3 , 25 $^\circ\text{C}$): δ = 6.90 and 6.75 (d, J =9.0 Hz, each 4H), 6.86 (s, 4H), 6.41 (d, J =3.6 Hz, 2H), 6.14 (d, J =3.6 Hz, 2H), 3.79 (s, 6H), 3.42 (s, 6H), 2.08 and 1.84 (s, each 6H); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (175 MHz, CDCl_3 , 25 $^\circ\text{C}$): δ =167.5, 158.3, 153.0, 133.9, 132.0, 131.9, 130.5, 129.1, 127.3, 121.6, 113.6, 110.4, 108.9, 55.3, 21.3, 25.0, 22.5; IR (CHCl_3): ν =1710 cm^{-1} ; HR-MS (ES): m/z = 645.2997, calcd. for $\text{C}_{40}\text{H}_{41}\text{N}_2\text{O}_6$ [$M + \text{H}$] $^+$: 645.2965.

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